

INVESTIGATION OF SELF CONFIDENCE LEVELS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ENGAGED IN INDIVIDUAL AND TEAM SPORTS

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Abstract:

Introduction and aim: In sports, self-confidence can be characterized by high-grade achievement expectation. In this context, the aim is to determine whether is any difference between the self-confidence levels of middle school students who do individual sports and those who are engaged in team sports. Age groups and gender as well as differences in self-esteem levels are also analyzed.

Method: The study group consisted of 96 students who were engaged in individual and team sports in 5 secondary schools in Istanbul. "Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory", developed by Coopersmith (1967), was used in order to determine self-esteem levels and the personal information form was prepared to collect participants' age, gender and sport type data. First, the Shapiro Wilk test was performed to test the distribution of the data and it was found that the data provided a normal distribution. Independent sample t-test was conducted to determine whether self-esteem levels differed significantly in terms of gender and age variables.

Findings: At the end of the study, the findings obtained from the data analysis showed that there was no significant difference in the self-confidence levels of the secondary school students compared to the sports types ($p > 0,05$). In the data obtained from other variables, it was determined that the level of self-esteem did not show any significant difference according to age and sex ($p > 0,05$).

Discussion: There was no significant difference between the presented study and the mean scores of confidence, age, sport type and gender ($p > 0,05$). It can be said that no

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definite decision has been reached on whether this self-confidence is influential or not according to the results of this sample and the results of the researches made. It is advisable to add lessons such as communication skills, human relations in order to improve curriculum self- confidence building levels in schools.

Keywords: self-confidence, secondary school, individual sport, team sport

1. Introduction

1.1 Self-confidence and self-sufficiency

It is known that many special factors are effective in the realization of learning in education and sports. Some of those factors are interest, motivation, attitude, problem solving skills, self-confidence and self-sufficiency. Success is increased by the fact that the skills are high, and when it is low is decreasing. When individuals feel confident and competent, they feel better in the learning process, and thus higher levels of learning come into play (Bilgin, 2011).

Self-confidence is a very important factor for the individual to have positive experiences, to feed himself / herself in the direction of his abilities and to support his / her strengths in the way of becoming a successful person (Ekinci, 2013). Self-confidence is defined as the individual's ability to recognize his / her feelings, self-love, and self-confidence (Özbey, 2004). Self-confidence can be positive or negative in relation to situations such as positive emotional development for the individual, self-love, thought to be sufficient, reconciliation with himself, and acceptance of himself / herself (Çelik, 2014).

Although the concepts of self-confidence and self-sufficiency are often confused, there is actually a difference between them. Self-sufficiency is the assessment of a person's abilities; self-confidence is the sense of ownership (Say, 2005).

In sports, self-confidence can actually be characterized by a high-level success expectation. Researchers have shown that safe athletes believe they have physical and mental skills that will bring out their potential to succeed, and more importantly, they will be successful (Yıldırım, 2013). The lack of confidence of the athlete brings with it failure (Rather and Singh, 2017). This suggests that self-confident athletes can be more calm and relaxed under stress and are better able to focus on more positive thoughts. Athletes and coaches have often indicated self-confidence as the most important mental skill for success (Vealey & Chase, 2008).

Sports activities, along with many other factors, affect the socialization of the individual. Particularly in sports games, the attitudes, values, norms, roles and skills of

the individuals are seen to develop during adulthood. Competitive emotions, work discipline, courage, sourness, struggle, accepting and defeating, shared emotions develop. The development of the sense of social responsibility results in social integration (Şahan, 2007).

Holt et al. (2011) investigated the effect of sport involvement on emotional control and psychological state in the study they performed, and observed that both the personal and social benefits of sports were observed in interviews with parents and children. In addition, social benefits have been reported in relation to coaches and friends in this study (Holt et al., 2011).

Self-confidence in the child is known to have passed through a term called trust or insecurity during the period from 0-12 months when viewed from a developmental perspective. In this period, the form of education, the way the child is raised and the emotional communication established with it lead to the formation of feelings of confidence or insecurity in the child (Cüceloğlu, 2003). It has been reported that sport participation is prevalent among 11-13 years old children, before entering adolescence (Zimmermann et.al, 2010). Young people who regularly participate in team sports during high school years are at a lower risk of developing depression in early adulthood. The number of years of individual sports participation did not show a statistically significant relationship with depressive symptoms in early adulthood. Based on these findings, team sport participation has been shown to protect against depressive symptoms in early adulthood (Sabiston et al., 2016).

1.2 Individual and Team Sports

A. Individual sports

This type of sports increases the power to struggle in the individual. An individual sport is that in which sports are made without entering into a struggle and mutual interaction with other individuals. With individual sports, the individual develops features such as self-confidence, self-control, quick decision-making, truthfulness, and protection of rights, and one becomes aware of his or her own abilities (Sahan, 2007). The individual approach seems to reflect the individual authenticity and the uniqueness of each person. It specifies the characteristics of a person's activity choice and a lifestyle in general (Kozina, 2009; Vargas & Short, 2011).

B. Team sports

Sports activities between teams consisting of at least two and more athletes such as football, basketball, volleyball, handball, korfbol are called team sports. Since success and failure are all disorganized, the athlete's responsibilities and spiritual constraints are less (Sahan, 2007).

1.3 Self-esteem

Self-esteem is the judgment of the individual and the attitude he/she has developed about himself/herself as the result of being evaluated and treated as an object. Self-esteem can be considered as an upper concept that is depicted with concepts such as self-importance, self-acceptance, or including these concepts (Kuzgun, 2000).

1.4 Respect for Your Relationship with Sports

The studies on the effects of sport activities on mental health generally focus on four dimensions, which are emotion-state, fear, depression and self-image. It is stated that there is a positive increase in emotion-state and self-perception depending on physical exercise, and a decrease in fear and depression (İkizler, 2002).

Man is an entity with individual and social needs. The nature of the sport also has functions such as sharing self-confidence, competition, respect, development of relationships with other people, winning and losing. In this sense, it can be considered that the achievements and skills achieved in the field of sports will help to acquire these qualities and contribute to the level of self-confidence of the individuals. The purpose of this study is to compare the self-confidence levels of secondary school students who are engaged in individual sports with team sports.

2. Method

2.1 Study Plan

The sample group of this research is composed of secondary school students who study in 5 secondary schools in the province of Istanbul in academic year 2014-2015 and who play in individual sports and team sports (96 students) All participants filled out a personal information form to determine their demographic characteristics.

The schools were determined as Istanbul Faik Reşit Unat Secondary School, Yıldız Tabya Secondary School, Çağrıbey Secondary School, Yunus Emre Secondary School and Öğretmen Harun Reşit Secondary School. The necessary explanations have been made by the researcher during the implementation of the scales. Permission has been obtained for the work done by the parents.

2.2 Data Collection Procedures

Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory Self-Confidence Scale form was developed by Coopersmith (1967) and adapted to Turkish by Pişkin (1997) and validated and credited by Akın (2007) as a data collection tool in the study. Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory

is a measurement tool with 25 items of self-esteem, including self-disdain, leadership-popularity, parent-family, assertiveness and anxiety, with a binary rating of yes-no.

2.2.1 Self-confidence scale

The self-confidence scale was developed by Akin (2007). The items of the self-confidence scale were written as a five-digit Likert ("1" Never, "2" Rarely, "3" Occasionally, "4" Generally, "5" Always) scoring scale and validity and reliability analyzes were conducted on these items.

2.3 Analysis of Data

The data obtained from the data collection tools were transferred to SPSS package program (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) and analyzed statistically. First, the Shapiro Wilk test was performed to test the distribution of the data and it was found that the data provided a normal distribution. Independent sample t-test was conducted to determine whether the descriptive statistics, self-confidence, and gender and age variables differed significantly in the evaluation.

3. Results

In this part of the study, findings about whether the self-esteem level of secondary school students who participated in the research varied according to sex, age and sport type are included.

Table 1: Statistical Results of Self Confidence Level by Sports Type

		n	Mean	Std. D.	P	T
Self-Confidence	Individual Sport	45	139,64	15,57	.299	1,04
	Team Sport	51	136,58	13,09		

P<0,05

The average scores of the secondary school students who participate in individual and team sports were found 139,64 and 136,58, respectively. There was no statistically significant difference in the T-test result between two groups ($p = 0.540$).

Table 2: Independent Variable T-test Statistical Results Self-Confidence
 According to Age and Gender

		n	Mean	Std.D.	P	T
Age	10-12	48	139,97	14,04	.181	1,34
	13-15	48	136,06	14,45		
Gender	Kız	48	139,66	14,71	.262	1,12
	Erkek	48	136,37	13,85		

P<0,05

The average score of the students in the 10-12 age group is 139.97, and the average of the students in the 13-15 age group is 136.06. There was no statistically significant difference between the scores of these two groups according to the independent T-test results ($p = 0.181$). The average score of female students in the same table was 139.66 and the average of male students was 136.37. There was no statistically significant difference between the scores of these two groups according to the independent T-test results ($p = 0.262$).

Table 3: Self-Esteem Statistics Results

		n	Mean	Std. D.	p	T
Respect the opinions of others	Individual Sport	45	4,62	,71	.419	,81
	Team Sport	51	4,49	,85		
I can ask questions to others if I do not understand	Individual Sport	45	4,57	,78	.393	,85
	Team Sport	51	4,43	,87		
I am a man of peace with myself	Individual Sport	45	4,53	,72	.103	1,64
	Team Sport	51	4,21	1,10		

P<0,05

In subjects with self-esteem level, the average scores of the secondary school students who perform individual sports were found higher than the students who played team sports. There is no statistically significant difference between the results of these two groups ($p > 0,05$).

Table 4: Results of Participation in Social Activities

		N	Mean	Std. S.	P	T
I do not mind participating in social events	Individual Sport	48	4,31	1,01	.019	2,39
	Team Sport	48	3,76	1,19		
I'm afraid to go to the foreground	Individual Sport	48	3,91	1,20	.585	,54
	Team Sport	48	3,78	1,06		
I can make friends easily	Individual Sport	48	4,37	,93	.234	1,19
	Team Sport	48	4,13	1,02		

P<0,05

The average scores of the items participating in social activities were found to be higher than secondary school students who play individual sports than those engaged in team sports. However, only a statistically significant difference was found between the results of these two groups in terms of participation in social activities ($p < 0,05$) but not in other parameters ($p > 0,05$).

4. Discussion

In this part of the study, the findings obtained as a result of the data analysis will be discussed in line with the aim of the study. The purpose of this study is to examine the self-confidence level of secondary school students in terms of various variables.

The most frequent positive results as a result of participation in sports are higher self-esteem, better social skills, less depressive symptoms, higher confidence and higher competence (Rochelle et al., 2013). In similar studies, it has been shown that sport participation is positively related between self-sufficiency (Inoue et al., 2015; Laborde et al., 2015) and self-esteem (Bjelica & Jovanovi, 2014; Eime et al., 2013).

As we can see social skills and socialization terms in the definition of self-confidence, it is shown that according to individual sports and team sports, students who engaged in team sports were more sociable (Yıldırım, 2011). In a similar study that examined the self-esteem levels of high school students who played individual and team sports in the same way, the team sports indicated higher self-confidence levels (Ekinci, 2014). However, in other studies, there was no significant difference in sense of athlete identity, courage and self-confidence in terms of team athlete and individual athlete distinction ($p > 0,05$) (Can and Kaçay, 2016). Likewise, in a study investigating the self-esteem from the sub-dimensions of the self-esteem concept, Çağlayan (2011)

found no significant difference between self-esteem scores of players who perform individual sports and team sports ($p > 0,05$).

In the present study, the self-confidence score averages for the secondary school students who perform individual sports were found to be 139.64 and 136.58, respectively. In this sample, the mean scores of the secondary school individual sport players were higher than team sport players but no significant difference was found. It can be argued that this sample and the different outcomes identified in the investigations made cannot reach a definite conclusion as to whether or not the sporting species being made has an effect on self-confidence.

There are studies showing that when they become adults, children become more active than those who were not physically active during childhood (Tammelin et al., 2003; Dunn et al., 2005). In a study examining whether the level of self-confidence in adolescents varied according to age, the self-confidence levels were found higher in younger ones than the older ones (Başoğlu, 2007). Umutlu (2010) found that the self-confidence levels of secondary school students under 12 years were higher than those who were 13-15 years in a study. In the present study, the mean self-confidence score of secondary school students for 10-12 years and 13-15 years was found to be 139,97 and 136.06, respectively. Although the average self-confidence scores of secondary school students aged 10-12 were higher than aged 13-15, there was no significant difference between them in terms of age. According to the results of this sample and other researches, it can be said that the self-confidence level of younger secondary school students is higher.

Sar et al. (2010) found in the results of the study in which examined the self-confidence levels of undergraduate students were examined in terms of sex and education that there was a significant difference between the self-confidence levels of undergraduates according to their sex. In a study conducted on adolescents, it was reported that self-esteem and self-confidence differed according to sex, for females, it is the self-esteem while for males, it is the self-confidence that was higher (Bilgin, 2011). Girls have a higher level of self-esteem than boys, and the study showed that adolescent girls had a higher self-esteem (Butcher, 1989). However, in a later study, it has been shown that men have more self-esteem than women (Kling et al. 1999). In the present study, the self-confidence score average of the girls and boys was calculated as 139.66 and 136.37, respectively. Although the self-confidence scores of the girls who were secondary school students were higher than boys, there was no significant difference between the self-confidence of the secondary school students in terms of gender variables ($p < 0,05$). According to the results of this study and the results of this research,

it can be said that no definite judgment has been reached about whether gender has an effect on self-confidence.

To Yıldırım (2011), it was determined that there is a significant difference in adolescents who play team sports as a result of comparing social skills and activity situations who perform individual and team sports. In another study, it was noted that the number of positive individuals in individual sports were systematically higher than team sports (Laborde et al., 2016). It has been reported that adolescents engaged in team sports are happier than other individuals (Zhou et al., 2015). In the present study, statistically significant difference was found only in the level of participation in social activities between secondary school students who engaged in individual sports and team sports. It can be said that secondary school students who engage in individual sport have more self-confidence in participating in social activities as well as in recognizing their own selves. There is a significant gender difference between symptoms of depression between males and female athletes (Wolanin et al., 2017). Several studies have shown that there is a significant difference in terms of symptoms of depression between team and individual athletes (Schaal et al, 2011; Nixdorf et al., 2013, 2016; Wolanin et al., 2016). Besides increasing physical activity levels, team sport participation has been reported to protect against despair and suicidal tendencies, (Taliaferro, 2008). Moreover, it was observed that entertainment and socialization were less in the individual sport players than in the team sport players (Elbe et al., 2017).

It can be stated that the different results that are found in this sample and in the researches made do not enable us to reach a definite conclusion about whether or not the type of sports activity is effective on self-esteem, social activity and communication.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

According to the findings obtained in this study, it can be said that female students have higher self-confidence level than male students. There is no statistically significant difference between the age groups. Although self-confidence level of those who do individual sports is higher than those engaged in team sports, there is a no statistically significant difference between the two groups.

In this study, it was analyzed whether the self-confidence levels of secondary school students varied according to their being engaged in individual sports or team sports status. Future work can be done with the participation of high school and university students. Lessons such as communication skills, human relations towards self-confidence development should be included in school curricula. There are many factors that affect whether self-confidence is low or high. From this point of view, it is

impossible for all of these factors to be presented in a study. Therefore, future studies should be done in such a way as to cover multiple variables.

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